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ENTREPRENEURIAL INITIATIVES IN RURAL TOURISM OF VOJVODINA

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ABSTRACT

Rural tourism originates and develops as a targeted activity to support tourists staying in rural areas. In the rural environment, business opportunities are limited, the infrastructure is often underdeveloped, the construction of business networks is difficult, and therefore the barriers for entrepreneurs are greater. For this reason, entrepreneurial initiatives in rural tourism are found in different forms and through the development of very special tourist products. The bearers of entrepreneurial initiatives are often women who economically valorize their work through rural tourism. The goal of the research is to determine the similarities and differences between initiatives in rural tourism, to identify the obstacles that were present, to determine the realized creative solutions, as well as the results of product placement on the tourist market. The method used in the research is a survey, and the applied technique is a semi-structured interview. The research established that there are very original entrepreneurial initiatives in rural tourism in Vojvodina, and the initiators are women, citizens' associations and farmers. Each initiative had its own development path, and the products they offer are based on authentic contents and local traditions.

KEY WORDS: entrepreneurial initiatives, rural tourism, product development, image of the region.

INTRODUCTION

As an alternative type of tourism, rural tourism is based on tourist infrastructure, products and services developed in rural areas and unique experiences of nature, tradition, customs and culture in the countryside. Rural tourism has gained importance with the growth of the urban population and the increase in the urbanization of cities. The urban population represents the

basic consumers of the offer of rural tourism. The urban population has a need for rest in a clean and preserved environment, they are oriented towards local gastronomy based largely on organic foods, they have a need to connect and socialize with hosts and locals. Therefore, rural tourism has a multifunctional role that enables the valorization and commercialization of various natural and anthropogenic elements which develop comparative advantages of rural communities.

According to Eurostat's urban-rural classification, rural areas in Serbia occupy about 80% of the territory of the Republic of Serbia, with about 63% of the total population living in these rural areas (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014). The agricultural and rural development strategy of the Republic of Serbia in the Priority Area 11 foresees a greater development of rural tourism. Namely, the diversification of economic activities and income transforms the rural economy by moving away from the activities of the primary sector of agriculture, industry, and tertiary activities. The improvement of the quality of life of the rural population will be encouraged by support for the regulation and renovation of the rural environment and the preservation of cultural heritage and natural wealth through projects of protection, conservation, and promotion of local architecture, landscapes, and other cultural, historical, and natural values (Agricultural and Rural Development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia, 2014; Ćurčić et al, 2021, 2). In addition, the Strategy for the Development of Tourism in Serbia and the Marketing Strategy for Tourism of Vojvodina established a selective approach, whereby rural tourism is treated as a priority within the alternative types of tourism (Muhi, 2013).

As a traditionally agricultural region, Vojvodina has excellent performance for the development of rural tourism and for the affirmation of rural life and traditions that have developed in a multicultural environment. Various entrepreneurial initiatives were launched through the furnishing and placement of accommodation facilities, the offer of gastronomic specialties, the offer of recreational activities (cycling and hiking, beaches on the shores of rivers and lakes, organized picnic areas, photo safaris, hunting and fishing), the placement of handicrafts and souvenirs and other. Starting and developing a business in rural tourism depended on the initial business idea, the knowledge of the entrepreneur and available financial resources (Ćosić, 2019).

The goal of the research is to determine the similarities and differences between business initiatives in rural tourism in Vojvodina, to identify

obstacles that were present when starting a business, to determine the realized creative solutions of rural tourism products, as well as the results of product placement on the tourism market.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN RURAL AREAS IN SERBIA

Entrepreneurial initiatives in rural areas are mostly related to agriculture, forestry and the service sector. Family farms are the most common form of business organization in the countryside, whose activities include plant production, livestock production, as well as fruit growing and viticulture. A smaller number of SMEs are involved in the production of flowers, tree seedlings, and vegetable seedlings. Also, in some regions there is production of honey, mushrooms, and snails. Thanks to the specific geographical natural conditions, certain regions have excellent conditions for the cultivation of vines and the development of wine tourism (Petrović et al., 2022), as well as the production of fruit and fruit brandies, liqueurs and juices. Forestry includes the planting, cultivation and commercial exploitation of private forests.

The service sector is represented through various craft services (modern and traditional crafts), mediation services, trade and catering services, health and educational services. The service sector plays a major role in raising the quality of life in the countryside and the smooth functioning of rural households. A developed service sector reduces the difference between urban and rural lifestyles, functionally improves the life of rural communities and influences the attraction of new rural residents.

Apart from the mentioned activities, the development of rural industries and their creativity (creative orientation), which require the adoption of a strategy for the construction of a new village, are increasingly mentioned. This can initiate a significant role of the creative economy in rural areas. Rural industrialization is the explanation for the success of SMEs (small and medium enterprises) in rural areas, and the creative industry is the context of their innovative and entrepreneurial potential (Rikalović et al., 2012). Creative industry in the countryside can include manufacturing industry, wine industry, art, marketing services, technology services, souvenir production and others. With the development of the creative rural industry, a greater arrival of experts and other workers who would settle in the villages is expected. In this way, greater economic revitalization of rural areas would be achieved, which would also affect demographic revitalization. Predictions of experts (Đekić, 2000)

point in that direction, who claim that agriculture is no longer the dominant branch in rural areas, because its importance is decreasing, while the attractiveness of other branches of the economy is increasing.

Rural tourism moved away from farm-stays – and grew into a complex business environment that today includes accommodation, food and beverage services, attractions, sports and nature-related activities, arts and crafts, museums, libraries, entertainment, etc. Many farms subsequently gave up on agriculture and focused on tourism alone, while new entrepreneurs, who were not farmers, moved from the cities to the countryside and also entered the rural tourism sector (Šajn & Finer, 2023, 2).

As an activity that positively affects GDP, employment, the balance of payments, investments, and the standard of living, tourism has great potential as an instrument to reduce regional inequalities. The positive effects of rural tourism are realized by increasing local production and the protection of rural areas. (Ćurčić & Mirković Svitlica, 2021, 55). The specificities of certain rural areas and attractions can be maximally used within the framework of rural development with the application of sustainable development principles. In rural areas, certain zones can be set aside for sports and recreation, for hunting and fishing, for cultural and spiritual content, for learning through the experience of working in the countryside, and more. By activating rural tourism, all the mentioned activities will gain a new economic dimension, and by placing complete packages of services, a new commercial value.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN RURAL TOURISM OF VOJVODINA

Rural tourism is seen by UNWTO to “make a real difference for rural communities, delivering jobs, supporting businesses and celebrating and protecting traditions” (UN Tourism, 2023).

In this sense, rural tourism is recognized as an economic activity that employs the rural population, diversifies their sources of income, and motivates young people to stay in the countryside. Also, viewed in a broader context, rural tourism contributes to the preservation of old traditions and customs, the presentation of cultural heritage, the production and marketing of handicrafts, the development of local gastronomy, innovations, and the branding of new destinations. So, profitable rural tourist product of Vojvodina should be at the center of the development, the integral part of which is a maximally preserved environment and cultural specificities of local community, accompanied by a

constant improvement of the experience quality of the visitors (Jegdić et al., 2017, 228).

As the northern province of the Republic of Serbia, Vojvodina covers 21,614 km² (27.9% of the territory of Serbia) and has about 1,744,000 inhabitants (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2023). Vojvodina is located in the southeastern part of the Pannonian Plain with a characteristic plain relief and a moderately continental climate. The hydrographic network is branched, and the plant and animal life is characterized by great diversity (Ćurčić & Terzić, 2024). Nature protection was achieved in the Fruška gora National Park, then in 16 special nature reserves, nine nature parks, three landscapes of exceptional characteristics, two protected habitats and a large number of nature monuments. Currently, about 138,000 ha or 6.4% of Vojvodina's territory is under protection (Puzović & Panjković, 2015),

In Vojvodina, the dominant rural regions are (Northern Bačka, Western Bačka,, Northern Banat, Middle Banat, Southern Banat, Srem district), and only one is designated as an intermediate region (Southern Bačka). In the population structure of Vojvodina, the urban population is 1,073,000 (61.53%), and 671,000 (38.47%) belong to the group of other population (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2023). Vojvodina is a culturally vibrant region, home to 26 nationalities and six official languages. Dominant ethnic groups are: Serbs, Hungarians, Romanians, Slovaks, Croats, Ruthenians, Muslims, and others which contribute to the multicultural and multireligious mosaic. Major industries in Vojvodina include agriculture, food industry, wholesale and retail, construction, energy, transport and communications, textile industry, electromechanical and related automotive industry, ICT, business services, logistics, and tourism (Development agency of Vojvodina, 2024).

Rural tourism has been developing since the end of the 1970s on a small scale, and it is getting its true expansion in the 21st century. Adopted strategic documents and sources of financing that were intended for rural tourism had a significant contribution to the faster development of tourism.

For some parts of Vojvodina are creating special Master development plans which includes tourism and where the proposed concrete measures and programs of activate already existing facilities (salashes¹) or building and

¹ Salash – a farm outside the village with a house and outbuildings, in which people reside permanently or occasionally, surrounded by fields. In the past, farms were temporary habitats of farmers and herders, which were transformed into permanent habitats over time (Ćurčić et al., 2010).

arrangement specific ecological sustainable tourist complex type of ethno-village, sports complex, arrangement coastal areas etc. On the area of Bačka are made Master plan of tourist complex „Uper Danube“ which provides for the revitalization of salashes in municipality of Sombor (project „Salashes on the north of Bačka“) with concretization activities in salashes and with complementary contents suitable to half day or one day tour (Стојановић & Манић, 2009; Ћурчић et al., 2010; Ћурчић & Павловић, 2011).

In Vojvodina, various tourism concepts based on entrepreneurship programs in rural communities are being developed: salash, ethno-houses, rural turist households, workshops, souvenir and old trades products shops, and an offer of organically produced food (Jegdić et al., 2017, 229).

Table 1 Territorial arrangement of rural tourism capacities in Vojvodina

District	Salash	Ethno-houses	Rural tourist households	Workshops, souvenir and old trade products shops
Nothern Bačka	9	4	1	0
Western Bačka	4	10	1	2
Southern Bačka	15	10	20	13
Srem	7	9	4	0
Nothern Banat	2	6	1	2
Middle Banat	1	6	0	2
Southern Banat	3	5	1	10
Total	41	50	28	29

Source: According to the data from Tourism Organization of Vojvodina, 2016 (Jegdić et al., 2017)

In Southern Bačka district, the largest number of all rural tourist facilities was recorded (58 facilities), followed by Srem (20) and Southern Banat districts (18) (Table 1). In the overall structure of facilities in rural tourism offer, ethno-houses (50) and salashes (41) are the most recorded, which indicates the economic involvement of original rural households with the offer of an authentic way of life and work in the countryside.

Rural tourism receives strong support through certain favorable credit lines and grants from relevant ministries (agriculture, tourism and youth), certain cross-border cooperation projects or some other international projects, which opens up space for launching new business initiatives and developing

complementarity between agriculture and tourism². In 2024, the Ministry of Tourism and Youth allocated around €1,270,000 in grants for the reconstruction and additional equipment of existing catering facilities for accommodation in rural tourism (N1info, 2024). 20 projects were approved for entrepreneurs from Vojvodina.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study uses comprehensive desk-research based on secondary data from key industry and academic sources. Field research included examining entrepreneurs in selected rural tourist households in Vojvodina. In collecting data from business owners in rural tourism, a survey method was used, and the applied technique was a semi-structured interview.

The sample provides an example of a business in rural tourism of Vojvodina. Three different examples of rural tourism development were analyzed (two on a farm and one in a rural tourist household). Two farms are located in the north of Vojvodina, in Bačka (surroundings of Sombor and Subotica), and the rural tourist household is located in Srem, near Fruška Gora. Specifically, Dida Hornjak's farm (Sombor), ethno-farm Balažević (Subotica) and rural tourist household Banstolka (Indija) were processed in the analysis. In the following text, the processed objects will be listed with abbreviations: DHF, EFB and RTHB.

In order to provide a complex overview of the research topic, the initial hypothesis was established: H0 Entrepreneurs recognized a good business opportunity in rural tourism.

Based on the initial hypothesis, four auxiliary hypotheses were derived:

H1 Entrepreneurs planned to engage in rural tourism.

H2 Entrepreneurs encountered obstacles when starting their rural tourism business.

H3 Entrepreneurs believe that they have good business results in rural tourism.

² In 2020, within the framework of the IPARD II program, "the allocation of grants related to the development of rural tourism is foreseen, which includes a wide range of investments, and in addition to the construction and reconstruction of facilities, it also covers investments in the purchase of equipment, the construction of accompanying facilities, children's playgrounds, landscaping of yards, area for tasting and selling food and drinks, sports fields, swimming pools, wellness facilities" (Vlada Republike Srbije, 2020).

H4 Entrepreneurs plan to improve the offer and products in the rural tourism business.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The three selected tourism entrepreneurial initiatives are an example of different beginnings and development of the rural offer in Vojvodina. Each entrepreneur had his own vision in which direction he should develop rural tourism with a strong reliance on his own sources of financing, as well as on project financing in the initial period. The knowledge gained through work and experience contributed to rural facilities building a recognizable image on the market (Table 2).

Table 2 Basic characteristics of selected rural tourism initiatives

	Dida Hornjak's farm (DHF)	Ethno-farm Balažević (EFB)	Rural tourist household Banstolka (RTHB)
Location	3 km from Sombor	Tavankut (Subotica)	Banstol (Indija)
Owner (m/f)	Female	HKPD „Matija Gubec“, non-government organization	Female, Farmer
Year of establishment	2008	2011	2003
Category	4*	1*	3*
Capacity	7 beds, 50 seats in the restaurant	12 beds, 120 seats in the restaurant+ terrace	10 beds, 50 seats in the restaurant
Basic services	Overnight stay, food	Overnight stay, food	Overnight stay, food
Additional services	Ethno-exhibition, agricultural works, feeding domestic animals, souvenirs,	Agricultural works, local events, gallery of straw paintings, souvenir shop,	Homemade products (jam, ajvar, juice, brandy), gathering fruits from nature,

	children's playground, carriage ride, horse riding	bicycle path, excursions	hunting, fishing, sports
Education for tourists	Workshops of old crafts, painting on glass and silk	Straw painting workshops, making souvenirs, folklore, preparation of winter pickle	Preparation of winter pickle, preparation of brandy
Shortcomings	Low profitability of rural tourism	Infrastructure is lacking (water supply, sewerage, not all streets are paved)	Lack of money to finish the pool

Through the processing of data collected in three rural tourist households, key answers will be presented in relation to the set hypotheses. Due to the limited scope of the work, only the most important information will be presented in the results.

Table 3 The way in which entrepreneurs started business in rural tourism

H1	Entrepreneurs planned to engage in rural tourism
DHF	<p>“I have always wanted to live on a farm and work in tourism after my sports career (handball). My goal was to make people feel good, to feel the spirit of the farm, history, culture, and to feel something they had forgotten or get to know something they never knew. And we succeeded.”</p> <p>“People like to go back in time, they long for the taste of their childhood, they like traditional Bačka dishes.”</p>
EFB	<p>“In fact, we started tourism in 2010 by accident, when the "Wealth of Diversity" project was launched. Out of a total of forty-five candidates, Tavankut entered the list of the ten most prepared villages. At that time, we were without a single accommodation capacity, without any necessary infrastructure, very young, without professional staff, and we educated ourselves about all this. But here it turned out to be a successful combination in the development of rural tourism.”</p>

	“Salaš Balažević bequeathed the association "Matija Gubec" to Jasna Balažević. We renovated it and equipped it for rural tourism.”
RTHB	“Since I was registered as an agricultural holding, and various contests were announced for the development of women in the countryside, I applied and received incentives from the Ministry of Agriculture. At the same time, I received a nice grant from the Directorate for Gender Equality at the contest for the development of rural women. That gave me so much wind at my back, I had both the will and the strength, I adapted the apartment and intended it for the reception of guests.”

Rural tourism as a profession for the two entrepreneurs was not planned and they started doing it quite by chance (EFB, RTHB). Certain circumstances and business opportunities led them to recognize a business opportunity and develop rural tourism. One respondent planned to engage in rural tourism on the farm and preserve the farm and tradition (Table 3). Answers dominate, according to which the entrepreneurs did not plan to engage in rural tourism, and therefore hypothesis H1 was not confirmed.

Table 4 Obstacles in the development of business in rural tourism

H2	Entrepreneurs encountered obstacles when starting their rural tourism business
DHF	“I first visited all the farms. I was at Majka's farm, Farm 137, Farm 84... I tried to see where I was. I realized that I was something completely different. They are my role models, but I don't copy them, because I am specific. I looked up to everyone a little bit. And when we went on study trips to Slovenia and Hungary, I pick up something good everywhere and try to improve it on my farm. Credits, standards, brand building - it's behind us now.”
EFB	“Of course, it was difficult at first, we were not well known. On the other hand, we didn't have enough promotional material or promotional space to be able to adequately present ourselves to the public. But we were known for our main brand – straw paintings. Our straw bales were somehow more quality to get people to come to Tavankut. Later, our overall offer expanded, as did our tourism product.”

RTHB	“The tourist household is far from the village and therefore there are many problems: there is no gas, low voltage, firewood should be provided. These are the obstacles we constantly struggle with.”
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Challenges and obstacles were present for all entrepreneurs when starting a business in rural tourism (Table 4). They started a business they knew nothing about, with no previous experience. They learned about rural tourism through work and from their mistakes, following the needs of the market. Over time, business experience has contributed to the development of the quality of the offer, as well as additional education and workshops attended by entrepreneurs. Therefore, hypothesis H2 is confirmed.

Table 5 Assessment of achieved business results in rural tourism

H3	Entrepreneurs believe that they have good business results in rural tourism
DHF	“It is my heritage and I am satisfied with the fact that I have preserved the farm and that I am maintaining it. People come, they leave with a full heart, they are satisfied. I gave them what I wanted. I am satisfied, but it can always be better and more.” “So far we have hosted thousands of tourists. Guests come from Germany, Italy, Switzerland, student excursions from Serbia and the countries of the former Yugoslavia. We have done a good thing and every year we have more and more tourists, which means that we are on the right track.”
EFB	“There are about 1,000 nights/year at the farm, guests stay for about 2 days. Over 80% of tourists come organized through travel agencies. Foreign guests mostly come from Croatia, Slovenia, Hungary, Bosnia and Herzegovina. Individual guests come from Austria, Italy, France. For us, one concrete live recommendation means more than any promotional material.”
RTHB	“Guests deserve the best and as long as you do that you have enough of them. My favorite thing is when the guests leave and then answer the phone, say: "Thank you and we'll come again." That's when I'm happiest.”

The general assessment of the entrepreneurs is that the achieved business results are good, that they attract tourists from the country and abroad, that the guests are satisfied after staying in their accommodation facilities. Also, entrepreneurs assess that they achieve good results thanks to the preserved

tradition of village life, loyal guests and word of mouth recommendations from guests (Table 5). Hypothesis H3 is confirmed.

Table 6 Plans for further business development in rural tourism

H4	Entrepreneurs plan to improve the offer and products in the rural tourism business
DHF	“The plans relate to the restoration and maintenance of the farm. We finance it mainly from earnings in agricultural activity, because earnings from rural tourism cannot cover all investments. We independently produce 70% of the foodstuffs needed for the development of tourism.”
EFB	“A tourist of the night in a rather modest setting. These are rooms, let's say, quite small, not all of them have TV or telephone connections and the like. That's why we want to build facilities for tourist accommodation in the coming period.”
RTHB	“With the arrival of guests from Iraq, who asked me if I was working according to HALAL standards, I decided to have a confirmation of what I was doing. We became the first holder of the HALAL certificate in rural tourism (food is prepared according to Muslim religious customs), which we received in 2020. At the same time, we had to fulfill the requirements for the HACCP certificate.” “An additional investment is needed to complete the hall where educational workshops would be held, and the construction of an outdoor swimming pool is also planned.”

Entrepreneurs have plans for further business development and for improving the offer of their rural household. New investments are planned mainly in accommodation facilities (construction or renovation) or in additional facilities (training hall, swimming pool) in order to develop new segments of higher quality offer. The development of products in the future is conditioned by the available sources of financing, that is, the speed of the inflow of money that can be invested in the further development of rural tourism (Table 6).

Based on the presented views, hypothesis H4 is confirmed.

Based on the answers received and a broader overview of the research topic, the key success factors for entrepreneurial initiatives in rural tourism were singled out. The key factors of success were singled out as a result of the entrepreneurs' experiences and their knowledge gained through learning in practice and on their own business development path:

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1. Recognition of personal potential
 2. Information, education and training related to starting a business
 3. Market research
 4. Investment in facilities, equipment, infrastructure
 5. Development of tourist product (package of services)
 6. Promotion development
 7. Placement and sale of products
 8. Networking and cooperation with other entrepreneurs
 9. Product quality improvement
 10. Expansion of the range of services, innovation
 11. Continuous analysis of business results

CONCLUSION

As a predominantly rural area, Vojvodina has good predispositions for the development of rural tourism. Rural tourism is gradually developing as a specific tourist product which offers elements of rural environment, nature, traditional hospitality and life values of local people (Ćurčić et al., 2010). Entrepreneurial initiatives are numerous and include several different forms of offer in rural tourism in Vojvodina (salash, ethno-houses, countryside households, workshops, souvenir and old trades products shops, and an offer of organically produced food). Starting a business and developing a product for each analyzed example is different, that is, the motives for entering rural tourism differ among entrepreneurs, as well as the knowledge and experience with which they started the business.

Creativity in the development of rural tourism products was conditioned by the initial resources and knowledge of entrepreneurs. Market experience, consumer reactions and consumer demands have led to the development of an offer that can best meet consumer expectations. In addition to the basic offer (accommodation, food), all entrepreneurs have developed additional offers as well as educational content for children and adults. The volume of supplementary and educational content in rural tourism affects the length of stay and the level of satisfaction of tourists. In all three examples, these contents are highly developed with further improvement tendencies.

The business results were rated as successful by all three entrepreneurs. However, the current volume of accommodation is not sufficient to satisfy all the needs of tourists and entrepreneurs consider it as a limiting factor for the

realization of higher income. Therefore, the investments they would undertake would be aimed at upgrading accommodation capacities and restaurants, that is, at increasing the basic resources for the provision of tourist services.

The countries of origin of tourists indicate that the demand for rural offers in Vojvodina is growing. Foreign guests, except from the region, come from most EU countries, from the Middle East, as well as from other continents. In this way, foreign and domestic guests show interest in rural tourism and confirm the quality of rural products in Vojvodina with their very positive reactions.

Rural tourism has confirmed itself as a good business opportunity in Vojvodina, the further development of which will certainly continue. Entrepreneurs expect strong support through project financing and the availability of money from domestic and foreign funds, as well as infrastructural equipping of rural areas as necessary conditions for faster progress. More and more young entrepreneurs are turning to rural tourism or just continuing the family tradition either as a basic or supplementary form of business. Project support for women in the countryside influenced women's empowerment and greater involvement in rural tourism, and women became the bearers of rural tourism development. In the long term, further business improvement of rural households can be expected with the mandatory nurturing and preservation of the authentic way of life and work.

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